

“DISINFORMATION IN DIGITAL POLITICAL DISCOURSE: A STUDY OF POLITICAL PARTIES IN PAKISTAN”

Mansoor Ahmad^{*1}, Muzna Yousfani²

^{*1}PHD Scholar and Faculty at Bahria University, Islamabad

²MS Scholar

¹ahmadmansur652@gmail.com, ²muznayousfani@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17959596>

Keywords

Disinformation, Misinformation, Forms of disinformation, Content Analysis, Facebook, Political Parties in Pakistan

Article History

Received: 17 October 2025

Accepted: 30 November 2025

Published: 17 December 2025

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Corresponding Author: *

Mansoor Ahmad

Abstract

In today digital world, the rapid proliferation of disinformation is one of the global risks and challenging issue. In this regard, the study investigated disinformation in digital political discourse of Pakistan that to what extent political parties in Pakistan engage in disinformation on social media. For this purpose, social media posts of four high profile political parties were manually analyzed. The researcher found that these political parties are highly indulged in disinformation, sharing disinformation for political agendas to achieve their political motive. Furthermore, these parties practice different disinformation trends and attributes to create confusion in public by sharing misleading and fabrication stories together. Misleading and fabrication were the most prominent attributes in Pakistan political landscape. Especially, misleading content is the most powerful and persuasive attribute of disinformation and calculated strategy in political communication of Pakistan. The study also showed that the prevalence of disinformation increases as the election time approaches.

INTRODUCTION

Disinformation is not a new phenomenon but digital revolution has made its proliferation faster and easier and it has brought drastic changes in all areas of human lives. Due to the changes brought by the digital revolution, today it disseminates so effectively on digital media platforms. New and advanced communication technologies are allowed advanced ways to create, share, and consume disinformation. It is not easy to differentiate what information can trust and what information to consume. Social media sites are the major source of news, information and political debate and politicians are the major players of spreading disinformation in political discourse (Recuero & Soares, 2018). According to Uzochukwu and Ekwugha 2014, virtual political campaigns are not only widely used for seeking supports but also discredit political parties

and political opponents through using unconfirmed news and propaganda on online social media platform, most prominently, Facebook WhatsApp, and Twitter are used for wide distribution of friendly and damaging speculative political messages. These social media content often has a strong effect on the outcome of elections and also on the country political stability and democratic system and outcomes of any political process or activity (Allcott and Gentzkow, 2017).

Now the information which continuously shared via the Internet and other social media platform shapes the opinions, mentalities and image of the world. This advancement in digital world and information technology has constructive in all walk of life in the modern world. It saves the precious time and give the benefits of doing work in very smart and intellectual

ways. It improved the access to these technological equipments and tools. However, along with this huge number of advantages this technological advancement has created complexities in different areas and domains of life from sharing to consuming information on internet. Such as in the area of the security domain, public trust and true information, because of these complexities digital world confronts some serious challenges of disinformation. These modern tools became dangerous weapons for many states and non-state actors. Because of this advancement, today, media tools have made it easier to launch online battles, information war and influence events at national and global levels (Svetoka, 2016). Now these social media information influence policies create untrue images, manipulating opinions and destabilizing political structure and unity (Rosenberger, 2020). In last decade, the attention has shifted and focused on growing levels of disruptive communication. Dissemination of disinformation on social media became prominence in 2016 during the United States of America presidential election, when people starting question on true news and authentic information. Now disinformation is one of the challenging issues and it influence have always been present in politics that created serious concerns for political leaders over security of elections and public trust in the democratic process (Schia & Gjesvik, 2020). (Recuero & Soares, 2018), investigated the Brazilian Presidential Election of 2018 and found that political parties and their followers played an active role in spreading disinformation, they shared huge amount of biased information on social media. Disinformation campaigns are used by regime or political actors to interfere in the dealings of another political actor, it frequently target citizens in democratic states at the time of elections (Trithara, 2020). Political Conversations on Twitter during the Brazilian Presidential Election of 2018 disinformation were widely shared by the pro-Bolsonaro media included misleading information, false poll results (fabricated information) or propaganda (false connection information and framing Bolsonaro in a “good” light (Recuero & Soares, 2018). Over the past decade, Concerns over disinformation in political discourse have intensified and emerged as a ubiquitous form of popular topic

among media scholars and media researchers in recent year. Online campaigning techniques are employed various social media platforms for creation of disinformation that distort democratic political processes, it is one of the biggest challenges and have the potential to influence political discourse, threatening healthy democracies and political engagement in all societies (Jones, 2019). Unfortunately for democracy, for its function and practice, disinformation will likely continue to be a rich and important area for future political communication and media research (Freelon & Wells, 2020).

The term Disinformation’ has been defined as false or manipulated information that distort reality and is knowingly shared to cause harm and mislead people (Jones, 2019). Disinformation includes all forms of misleading and false information constructed, designed, and promoted deliberately or intentionally to cause public harm (European, 2018). Disinformation is a type of information but it is misleading Information and that misleading information is none accidentally (Fallis, 2015).

Digital media are interactive online platforms that facilitate the creation, distribution and sharing of content with online community. According to Haase & Peet, 2017, social media are internet based platforms, which provide online services to users and enables them to communicate by building their online community. Digital media has become part of our lives; however, experts and common people have serious concerns over the spread of fake news and creation of disinformation and started question the true information in political discourse on social media and want to make it trustable tool for news and information.

Pakistan media have confronted serious challenges in different eras. After 2002, the Pakistani media has seen a rapid growth and number of mainstream channels increased in Musharraf Era. According to PEMRA, there were approximately 90 TV channels in 2012. Likewise, Social media platforms have experienced rapid growth in Pakistan, with approximately 53 active million users in 2021, reflecting a 9 percent increase from the previous year. Media Ownership Monitor Pakistan report, 2018, the media landscape in Pakistan has undergone remarkable growth and transformation until 2018,

emerging as one of the most dynamic within South Asia (Rehmat, 2019). This evolution was characterized by the spread of media outlets, including thousands of newspapers, more than 100 television channels, and 200 active radio stations working across cities in the country. All competing for public attention and today all these channels have strong presence on social media.

Challenges confront by Social Media users in Pakistan are awareness, literacy, Ethical Issues, Security and privacy Issues and disinformation campaigns by government (Memon & Mahar, 2015), which make it harder to identify misinformation on social media by users. Social media has been used in Pakistan as an advocate for social issues and it facilitates political debate (Ali & Jan, 2013). Digital media sites, these days, are the major source of news, information and political debate in Pakistan. Social media in Pakistan break news stories that are ignored by print and electronic media.

Social media are very useful tool for promotion of democracy, the political parties get very effective platform to communicate with audience. However, alongside its benefits and usefulness, there are negative implications as well. Politician are highly engage and excessively use social media to promote their agenda, they hire people to manage their social media platforms For example, politicians can engage in disinformation to mislead and misinform the people. Social media sites are the major source of news, information and political debate and politicians are the major players of spreading disinformation in political discourse (Recuero & Soares, 2018). The audiences and voters were badly exposed to this fake news phenomenon (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017). Many studies have been conducted on disinformation in political discourse in western countries, still there was need to investigate that to what extent the political parties in Pakistan engage in disinformation while promoting their political agendas. Therefore it was important to investigate that to what extent political parties in Pakistan engage in it and what strategies they apply to spread disinformation. So, the study added knowledge to existing scholarship from Pakistani setting.

Thus, many researchers have investigated disinformation in political discourse in western

countries and they have found widespread attributes and indicators of disinformation in political discourse. So, this study is one of the attempts to investigate that how the political parties engage in disinformation in Pakistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the past decade, Concerns over disinformation in political discourse have intensified and emerged as a ubiquitous form of popular topic among media scholars and media researchers in recent year. Disinformation theory is popular in the field of information. Disinformation can be defined as distribution and dissemination of false or misleading information with deliberate attempt to mislead the audience(s) distort reality by harming other (Rizi, 2020). Disinformation is information that spread intentionally, this misleading content disseminated for political purpose that resembles trustworthy and authoritative information (Trithara, 2020).

To respond effectively to this concern and issue, we first need to clearly understand and define the phenomenon. Disinformation is not entirely a new phenomenon, but it is newly salient, misleading public against opponent with disinformation is nothing new. The advancement in technology and digital age has changed how such kind of information and messages are created, distributed, circulated, and interpreted with their strong potential effects and the way how it changed and influence voter behavior and view of political discourse. According to (Chadwick et al. 2018), disinformation can be seen as “intentional behavior that purposively misleads and harm. In contrast, misinformation differs from disinformation as there is no intention to harm or deceive (Jack 2018). While malinformation requires a factual basis and based on reality but inflict harm and deceive.

Realizing the significant effect of false information on a global scale, academia, national, international, and other organizations try to first understand and then act against the phenomenon. In the literature, there are many terms and concepts that are used to refer to false, untrue, or half-true information such as fake news, false news, digital misinformation, disinformation and rumors. These terms have been used by different researchers and experts, Zhou and Zafarani, 2018, Lazer et al., 2018 use the term fake

news, the term false news has been used by Vosoughi et al., 2018, World Economic Forum, 2018 used the term digital misinformation, (Shao et al., 2018) used the term rumors while (Amazeen and Bucy, 2019; HLEG, 2018; Wardle and Derakhshan, 2017) used the word disinformation.

There is another term mostly people mix it with the term 'propaganda that cause confusion. As used in Article 20(1) of the 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, it 'refers to the conscious effort to mould the minds of men [sic] so as to produce a given effect'. So can say that disinformation is therefore a subset of propaganda. Propaganda includes both true and false selective and persuasive information and material to influence, but in case of disinformation there is only false, fabricated or manipulated information that is intentionally and knowingly shared to cause harm. Both propaganda and disinformation techniques are widely uses in political spectrum on social media platforms to cause confusion and mislead people. Disinformation and other similar challenges have potential to affect all political activities and political discourse, undermine political system and threatening political engagement not only in healthy democracies but in all societies.

Misinformation and disinformation on digital media platforms can cause serious harms. It can undermine the integrity of elections; destabilize political systems, and derailing public health messages. But still media scholars and experts struggle to agree on definitions of these terms. Spreading false or inaccurate information is an old phenomenon but the different today is the speed and the global reach. Digital media enable people to spread false information more rapidly via different social media network (Benkler et al., 2018).

In politics the term disinformation means repercussions, ranging from legitimate propaganda to election manipulation. The term 'Disinformation' has been defined as false or manipulated information that distort reality and is knowingly shared to cause harm and mislead people (Jones, 2019). (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2018) study focuses on the term disinformation, according to the level of falseness and/or intent to cause harm: misinformation (false, but not intentionally created to harm); disinformation (deliberately created to cause harm);

and mal- information ((based on reality, but used to inflict harm) (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2018). Fabricated information and political speech are the opinions, false and unverified claims, factually inaccurate and viewpoints that are not authentic and these untrue information refer as true and correct, and there are lack of references, expert knowledge and empirical evidence (Hameleers, Populist Disinformation: Are Citizens With Populist Attitudes Affected Most by Radical Right-Wing Disinformation?, 2022). Disinformation is basically an attack on the integrity of knowledge, the information environment become pollutes when people start believe on circulated disinformation to be true (Tsipursky, 2017).

Today Democracies around the world confront rising levels of disinformation as a serious concern and threat. The intentional spread of these falsehoods and fabricated information and related attacks on the rights of minorities, press freedoms, and the rule of law all these challenge the basic norms and values on which institutional legitimacy and political stability depend. The fairness of democracy and political processes is destabilized in the digital era by spreading of disinformation techniques and campaigns, which may destroy the accuracy of public debate and strongly influence public opinion on different policy issues (Cianci & Zecca, 2023). (Olan, Jayawickrama, & Suklan, 2022) argue that disinformation lead people to question accurate and true information.

Jones 2019 argues that many varieties of disinformation include: politicians lying about their policies and political activities; attacks on the scientific evidence surrounding important issues such as climate change; the spread of "deep state," "globalist" and various conspiracy theories; and the invention of stories to inflame existing social and political conflicts. (Hameleers, 2022) argues that disinformation also destabilize political stability and threaten democratic values. (Piazza, 2022) argues that online disinformation increase and sharpens political polarization in society. As (Iyengar, Lelkes, Levendusky, Malhotra, & Westwood, 2019) research study has shown that political polarization has grown dramatically in the United States. Similarly (Reiljan, 2020) stated in his study that political polarization increased in many countries in recent years.

The sources of these claims include elected politicians, movement leaders, social media influencers, foreign governments, and political information sites that often use familiar journalistic formats to package propaganda. Many of these efforts come from the radical-right movements, parties and wealthy libertarian interests that oppose broad and inclusive democratic representation, and the public interest protections of government (Jones, 2019).

Online campaigning techniques are employed through various social media platforms for creation of disinformation that distort democratic political processes, it is one of the biggest challenges and have the potential to influence political discourse, threatening healthy democracies and political engagement in all societies (Jones, 2019). Politicians are highly engaged and excessively use social media to promote their agenda, they hire people to manage their social media platforms. For example, politicians can engage in disinformation to mislead and misinform the people. Social media sites are the major source of news, information and political debate and politicians are the major players of spreading disinformation in political discourse (Recuero & Soares, 2018). The audiences and voters were badly exposed to this fake news phenomenon (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017). Populism around the world uses disinformation techniques and is highly involved in spreading disinformation via social media platforms. Former American president Donald Trump is one of the examples; during the time of President Donald Trump 1,055 days in office, he had misled or lied to the American people 15,413 times (Bennett & Livingston, 2018). The disruptive communication and the decline of democratic institutions (M. Hameleers, 2020) indicated that the political leaders Donald Trump and Geert Wilders blame media in populist ways and consider them as part of the corrupt and lying establishment.

Evidence shows that voters were badly exposed to fake news, widely shared in favor of Donald Trump (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017). In the field of politics, the impact of fake news on the public has been identified in democratic systems such as the presidential elections in the United States (2016), the presidential elections in France (2017), in 2018 Mexico and Italy presidential election, UK Brexit

deal or the referendum on the permanence of The United Kingdom in the European Union (2016) (Perez-Curiel & Velasco Molpeceres, 2020). The University of Oxford's Computational Propaganda Research Project surveyed in 2018 worldwide and found evidence of disinformation or manipulated media in 52 countries out of 70 countries surveyed in 2018, it includes democratic and non-democratic nations ranging from Italy and Germany to Brazil, China, South Africa and Nigeria.

In 2018 Twitter reported that our systems identified more than 9.9 million potentially spammy or automated illegal bots accounts per week used for spreading false or disinformation, similarly a large amount of Facebook pages data has influenced political sentiment all over the world. (Dehghan & Glazunova, 2020) explores the strategic use of 'fake news' discourses in non-democratic contexts and found that social media platforms serve to influence discourses where politicians employ the discourse as a means to strategically delegitimize and discredit their opponents. The study addressed two key questions, what are the key components of disinformation as practiced by political parties? And to what extent do the political parties in Pakistan engage in disinformation while promoting their political agendas?

Theoretical Framework

Disinformation theory is grounded and supported by the current studies of disinformation in digital political discourse; this theory is more related to our study. Disinformation theory is popular in the field of information. Disinformation can be defined as the distribution and dissemination of false or misleading information with a deliberate attempt to mislead the audience(s) and distort reality by harming others (Rizi, 2020). Disinformation theory entails the distribution, sharing and dissemination of false, mistaken and misleading information in an intentional, deliberate, effortful and purposeful agenda-based attempt and effort to harm, deceive and confuse or create fear for political purposes (Fetzer, 2004).

Disinformation is information that is spread intentionally, these misleading contents disseminated for political purposes that resemble trustworthy and authoritative information (Trithara, 2020).

When the source of information is acknowledged in disinformation it is called overt disinformation but when the source is concealed it is called covert disinformation (Fetzer, 2004). **Disinformation** is completely false or misleading piece story or information share with the intention to deceive or cause harm. It can appear in different forms fabricated, misleading, false context, false connections or deliberately manipulated audio/visual or texted content, intentionally created conspiracy theories or rumors spread to harm or cause distrust in public. There are many examples, when a social influencer intentionally changes scientific facts to support his/ her conspiracy theory, its disinformation. Disinformation is when politicians share selected piece of information or made up facts which support their arguments to deceive and mislead people, distorts reality. Misinformation and disinformation on digital media platforms can cause serious harms. It can undermine the integrity of election; destabilize political systems, and derailing public health messages. But still media scholars and experts struggle to agree on definitions of these terms.

There are some key characteristics to measure disinformation; it includes harmful content, hate speech, unverified content to harm other and terrorist incitement (Tan, 2022). Disinformation involves a constellation of media genres (Freelon & Wells, 2020) and clickbait headlines, misleading use of statistics, captions, images or as well as the original content that is shared out of context, (It includes imposter content, manipulated and fabricated content) (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2018).

We exclusively look at disinformation in the political context that created and disseminated to destabilize political system and governments, strengthen distrust, doubt, created confusion and polarization (Bennett & Livingston, The disinformation order: Disruptive communication and the decline of democratic institutions, 2018). Messages credibility are important to investigate disinformation on three different levels, the statements or content of the message, source of the message, and style of the message that how it presented (Hameleers, Populist Disinformation: Are Citizens With Populist Attitudes Affected Most by Radical Right-Wing Disinformation?, 2022).

Extending Western scholarship and define Falsehoods or rumours knowingly Propagated as part of a political agenda and this can achieve viral status whether or not there is malicious intent and it is Part of state-sponsored disinformation campaigns (Gibbons & Carson, 2022). Stanford University provides the definition that “the information that are verifiably false and intentionally mislead readers. Disinformation involves purposeful manipulation, de- contextualization, or fabrication of untrue information to achieve a predefined political goal (Freelon & Wells, 2020). Disinformation is a type of information but it is misleading Information and that misleading Information is none accidentally (Fallis, 2015).

Outright lie: Outright lies (total falsehoods) are complete false statement that is intentionally false and meant to deceive. Fabrication : In academic research, fabrication is the deliberate misrepresentation of results through invented facts or made-up data and designed to deceive people and do harm. It is completely false content.

Misleading: Content is often misleading when the framing of a situation is misrepresented. It’s about cropping photos, or choosing statements or statistics selectively in order to support an argument. For example, presenting comment as fact. Satire/parody : Another source of content that can be found online is satirical news, defined as an intentionally false story meant to be perceived as unrealistic, that uses journalistic style as a parody of the style, to mock issues and individuals in the news, or to disseminate a prank (Frank, 2015; Reilly, 2013).

Sensationalism is one of another disinformation form: Half-truths contain elements of sensationalism which reinforce the falsehood and deception of a message (Asubiaro & Rubin, 2017). The use of ‘deep fakes which is already explained in literature above is also one of disinformation creation form such as audio and video whose fabrication is increasingly difficult to detect (by humans or algorithms). Deepfake video is one of another form of disinformation: Deepfake videos are forms of disinformation that not only affect public trust and political leader reputation and image but also threaten the individual’s political success and create a sense of misunderstanding over what is real and what is not. These deepfake videos are

disinformation because they originate with intentional acts to harm opponent political leader. These deepfake videos are disinformation because they originate with intentional acts to harm opponent political leader. (Dobber, 2020) provides a first comprehensible support for the idea that deepfakes are more powerful form of disinformation than false news stories studied by Bail et al. (2020) in the Russian Twitter trolls and Guess et al. (2018).

METHODOLOGY

This study has quantitative nature and applied content analysis method to analyze the data manually that to what extent political parties in Pakistan engage in it and what strategy they apply to disinform people and how are discourses of reality, and disinformation connected in politicians' communication.

Social media is digital technology and online platforms that allows the sharing of ideas and information, including text and visuals, through virtual networks and communities. In this study we analyzed Facebook posts of different political parties in Pakistan. Total time duration selected for data gathering are 8 months, 4 months before election and 4 months after election. This is the period that marks heightened activities on the 2023 general elections in Pakistan and there is possibility of sharing disinformation for legitimating and delegitimizing political candidates and parties. Sample for the study included 4 political parties and their official facebook pages, 300 posts analyzed from each party official facebook page. Total 1200 posts were analyzed. Systematic random sampling was used to analyze data. Data Analysis: Data were manually analyzed of 1200 posts. In this study the researcher measure disinformation variables used in previous studies that relate with local setting. Outright lies (total falsehoods) are complete false statement that is intentionally false and meant to deceive. It involves stating something that the speaker knows to be untrue with the intention to mislead others by DePaulo, 1996, Bavelas et al. (1990).

A statement or text contains complete false information (Green, 2004). In this study outright lie is one of the variables categories, it has been taken to define it as the complete false and unauthentic information and statement meant to intentionally

disseminate to disinform and deceive. Outright lie is complete false statement require more effort, outright lie tellers providing complete false information (Caso, Cavagnis, & Dunbar, 2023).

میں 2017 میں آٹا 35 روپے چھوڑ کر گیا تھا روٹی چار روپے کی تھی چینی 50 روپے کلو تھی پیٹرول 65 روپے لٹر تھا سونا 50 ہزار روپے تولہ تھا ہم نے اس وقت پاکستان کی ترقی کیلئے کسی کے آگے ہاتھ نہیں پھیلائے صدر مسلم لیگ (ن) محمد نواز شریف

This news report and statement shared by PMLN on Facebook are completely false statement and outright lie as it opposed by different main stream news channel, such as GEO NEWS, EXPRESS NEWS, SAMMMA NEWS and other news Channel as well. In academic research, fabrication is the deliberate misrepresentation of results through invented facts or made-up data and designed to deceive people and do harm by Research guide, SSU, 2022. Fabricated information are the opinions, false and unverified claims, factually inaccurate figures, data and viewpoints that are not authentic and these untrue information refer as true and correct, and there are lack of references, expert knowledge and empirical evidence, (Hameleers, Populist Disinformation: Are Citizens With Populist Attitudes Affected Most by Radical Right-Wing Disinformation?, 2022). News stories are simply made-up and have no basis in reality by Bente Kalsnes 2018. It is completely false content. In this study fabrication is the category where information falls that has been made up to misrepresent the data and facts are invented by the politicians in their own favor which is not correct. It serves the same purpose to deceive and create confusion in public.

عداد و شمار اور شواہد سے وزیر اعلیٰ مریم نواز کے 16 ہفتے پیپلز پارٹی کے سندھ میں 16 سالہ حکومت پہ بہاری ہیں

Another example of disinformation shared by one of the political parties on Facebook found in this study where facts and figure are made up and complete fabricated story.

Content is often misleading when the framing of a situation is misrepresented. Misleading content often pretends to be objective while arguing a particular point of view; it aims to mislead the result

of content by Research guide, SSU, 2022. It's about cropping photos, or choosing statements or statistics selectively in order to support an argument. For example, presenting comment as fact. Misleading information may true but incomplete statements, a statement that may be misleading cannot be said to have lied (Green, 2004).

Half-truths presented in such a way as to place a person or an issue in a negative light. In this study misleading information is another category, in this form of disinformation, the statement and information may be correct but not complete and miss a particular point of view. A correct and true information needed both side of the story and complete information but misleading information are choosing statements or statistics selectively in order to support an argument to mislead the result or data.

پاکستان میں 175 سیاسی جماعتیں ہیں لیکن کسی نے بھی پاکستان تحریک انصاف کی طرح صاف شفاف اور آئین کے مطابق انٹرا پارٹی الیکشن نہیں کروائے

The claim in this statement has misleading content. As according to above definition this statement is misrepresented and pretends to be objective while arguing a particular point of view, presented comment and selective opinion as a fact. According to study of Mehmood, A., & Khan, S. (2020), In Pakistan, mainstream political parties included PTI avoided intra-party elections and top leadership through direct nomination. Imran Khan also followed the traditional interparty election culture as other political parties do except JI, despite his long-held claims of change in Pakistan's political culture (Yasin, 2017).

Potential to harm: Potential to harm content harmful for citizens and society at large includes illegal forms of speech', such as defamation, hate speech, and incitement to violence, it refer to a range of information which causes harm, intentionally or unintentionally usually in relation to the promotion of a particular moral or political cause or point of view and that particular information and statement cause harm for public (Fathaigh & Helberger, 2021).

Potential to harmful content including harm to a person, social group nation and public harm, this public harm is, subsequently threats to democratic political system, social ethics, values, evoke emotions to damages that cause harm in different areas such as politics, education, economy, health, science, education and other (Wardle & Derakhshan, 2018). In this study the last variable is potential to harm, we defined this category of variable as any information that has the ability and potential to harm public or opponent political leaders. The information that is not lie in first three categories of variables but has the potential to harm has placed in this category.

اقتدار کیلئے ریاست پہ حملے کرنے والو اپنے ضمیر سے پوچھو کیا تم پاکستانی ہو؟ ان کا ہر اقدام ریاست مخالف اقدام ثابت ہوا ہے، ریاستی اداروں پہ حملہ ہو یا ملکی سالمیت پہ حملہ ان سب کے پیچھے تحریک انصاف ہی کھڑی نظر آئی جو کام پاکستان کا بدترین دشمن نہ کر سکا نہ اسے ایسا کرنے کی ہمت ہوئی وہ کام ہمارے درمیان رہ کر تحریک انصاف کے لوگوں نے کر دکھایا۔

DATA ANALYSIS

The study aimed to analyze that to what extent the political parties in Pakistan engage in disinformation while promoting their political agendas and to know trends and attributes of disinformation develop by political parties in Pakistan. As in the first step we investigate the distribution of disinformation produced by selected political parties on Facebook and to what extent these political parties engaged in disinformation.

RQ1: What is the distribution of disinformation produced by selected political parties on facebook?

Distribution of Disinformation Attributes	
Political Party	Total N(%)

JI N (%)		PMLN N (%)	PPP N (%)	PTI N(%)	
Outright lies	0 (0)	8(3)	9 (3)	15 (5)	32 (3)
Fabrication	1 (0)	42(14)	18(6)	19(6)	80(7)
Misleading	28 (9)	75(25)	71(24)	104(35)	278(23)
Potential to Harm	1 (0)	23(8)	4(1)	19(6)	47(4)
None of these	270 (90)	152(51)	198(66)	143(48)	763(67)
Total	300 (100)	300(100)	300(100)	300(100)	1200(100)

X²(12, N=1200) 182.34 p value 001

The above table provides a detailed analysis of how different political parties in Pakistan (PTI, PMLN, PPP, and JI) engage in disinformation, categorized as "outright lies," "Fabrication," "Misleading," and "Potential to harm."

PTI has the highest overall disinformation, leading in misleading content (34.7%) and outright lies (5%). PTI's disinformation includes harmful and fabricated content, reflecting its reliance on distorting facts while PMLN has the second-highest disinformation, 25 percent of misleading but PMLN leading in fabrication (14%) and harmful content (7.7%). This suggests aggressive disinformation tactics that combine fabrications with potentially harmful content. In this study the researcher applied

Chi-Square test to see the difference in distribution of disinformation produced by political parties among and found Asymptotic Significance (2-sided, p-value = 0.001). The p-value is 0.001, suggesting that the relationship between the political parties and the types of disinformation is statistically significant. Since the p-value (0.001) is less than the common significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), indicates that there is significant difference in the distribution of disinformation among political parties. This means there is a statistically significant relationship between the political parties (JI, PMLN, PPP, PTI) and the forms of disinformation. In other words, the distribution of disinformation varies significantly across the political parties.

In the next step we analyzed the second question which is about political parties' engagemen Report

Political Party	Comments	Likes	Shares
JI	34.75	1825.89	190.00
PMLN	133.12	1493.20	121.84
PPP	40.43	792.60	105.18
PTI	40.64	2075.83	191.77
Total	61.98	1534.38	152.28

PMLN, while not leading in likes or shares, excels in generating the most discussions through comments (133), reflecting high follower engagement. PPP shows the lowest engagement across Likes, shares, and comments but maintains consistent interaction without major fluctuations in engagement levels.

Next the researcher analyzed disinformation form with engagement. Which disinformation form received the higher engagement?

Disinformation 1	Comments	Likes	Shares
Outright lies	40.59	1354.22	166.22
Fabrication	80.52	1376.31	131.89
Misleading	104.05	1711.85	169.48
Potential to harm	98.91	1429.34	158.79
Total	61.98	1534.38	152.28

The above table provides a statistical overview of different categories of disinformation based on engagement. Misleading and Fabrication categories have the highest average comments, showing that people tend to comment more on content that is not totally and clearly false but made up facts and misrepresents facts. Misleading categories received

the most likes on average. Outright lie had the highest average sharing category indicating that content that is entirely false tend to be shared more often.

To what extent the various disinformation forms are correlated to each other?

Correlations

Outright Lie		Fabrication	Misleading	Potential to Harm	
Outright lie	Pearson Correlation	1	.388**	.211**	-.015
Fabrication	Pearson Correlation	.388**	1	.531**	.048
Misleading	Pearson Correlation	.211**	.531**	1	.192**
Potential to Harm	Pearson Correlation	-.015	.048	.192**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table shows Pearson correlations between different types of disinformation: Outright lie, Fabrication, Misleading and Potential to Harm. There is strong correlation between fabrication and Misleading Information: These two types of disinformation have the strongest positive correlation (0.531), they are frequently found together. Posts that contain fabricated content are more likely to also be misleading. Outright Lies and

Other Types: Outright lies show a moderate correlation with fabrications (0.388) and a weak correlation with misleading information (0.211). At final stage we explored and analyzed whether spread of disinformation increase as the election come close or remain same

Is the Prevalence of disinformation increases as the elections time approaches?

The above graph shows different time period from November, 2023 to June 2024. There is a noticeable spike or peak in disinformation in February 2024, which was election month, as the general election 2024 took place on 8th of February 2024. We found and noted a high peak and spike of disinformation during this period; this suggests that disinformation activities on social media intensify as elections approach. From November 2023 to January 2024,

the number of disinformation events is generally low, but we have seen rapid increase in disinformation when January month start, specifically from the mid of the January till Election Day. After February, following party on social media, PTI engages in the most diverse types of disinformation, particularly in the misleading category. PMLN has the second highest number of misleading post of their overall disinformation

while they leading in fabrication and potential to harm information and outright lies make up smaller percentage. Political Conversations on Twitter during the Brazilian Presidential Election of 2018 disinformation were widely shared by the Pro-Bolsonaro media included misleading information, and fabricated information (Recuero & Soares, 2018). PPP has also the similar number of content falls under misleading, but less PMLN and PTI with some fabrication but fewer outright lies. JI Interestingly, Jamaat-e-Islami (JI) has the least engagement in disinformation, with 90 percent of their content showing no disinformation, and only

dissemination of disinformation decreased but continues to appear at irregular intervals until June 2024, with occasional smaller spikes. This suggests that disinformation efforts by politicians and political parties ramp up significantly during politically sensitive times, like elections.

Discussion

Social media platforms are the most powerful tools use by political leaders to advance their political agenda by adopting different forms and attributes of disinformation. As in this study the researcher finds that different political parties in Pakistan indulged in disinformation activities in Pakistan. The most 1/10 content found in misleading category. This suggests that JI is least involved in sharing disinformation compared to other parties. These findings and number suggest that political parties and political leaders in Pakistan indulged in disinformation dissemination on their social media platforms, especially misleading content, is a calculated and organized technique and strategy in political communication in Pakistan political discourse with profound implications with how social media users perceive truth and form opinions in Pakistan’s political landscape. As (Memon & Mahar, 2015) and (Ali & Jan, 2013) argued that Challenges confront by Social Media users in Pakistan are awareness, literacy, Ethical Issues, and disinformation campaigns by government. This lack of awareness and media literacy in Pakistan make it difficult for public to choose the right candidate as

argued by (Achen & Bartels, 2016) that in democratic system, a well informed and rational voters guide the country to choose the right candidate only, all this need is the public knowledge, media literacy and responsibility of press to hold the government and other institutions of democratic government accountable by sharing accurate news stories and authentic information with audience. The political scientists Christopher H. Achen and Larry M. Bartels argued in their book (*Democracy for Realists: Why Elections Do Not Produce Responsive Government*) that poorly informed, misguided and misinform citizens about issues and policies people do not produce better democratic government. The researcher examined that people use social media for political debate and share social media posts of their favorite political leaders irrespective of disinformation factor. As (Ali & Jan, 2013) argues that Social media has been used in Pakistan as an advocate for social issues and it facilitates political debate. According to (Recuero & Soares, 2018) Social media sites are the major source of news, information and political debate and politicians are the major players of spreading disinformation in political discourse. These findings suggest that these politicians are aware of how to use social media to mobilize public and how to utilize these social media platforms for political agendas to build strong opinion in public mind. As argued by (Ali & Jan, 2013) that Pakistani politicians are aware to utilities social media for political purposes to gain popularity and build their soft image before election. These online disinformation campaigning techniques are employed via various social media platforms for producing disinformation is one of the biggest challenges and have the potential to influence political discourse (Jones, 2019). The researcher found in this study that Pakistani politicians and political parties are highly engaged in disinformation dissemination on social media pages. These politicians are highly engage and excessively use social media to promote their agenda, they hire people to manage their social media platforms and politicians are the major players of spreading disinformation in political discourse (Recuero & Soares, 2018).

The data suggest that disinformation strategies vary significantly across political parties, with PTI being

more engaged in misleading content, which is likely more subtle and complex than outright lies or fabrications. The larger percentage of misleading information suggests a calculated disinformation approach that blends facts and falsehoods, making it more difficult to refute. On the other hand, PMLN and PPP are somewhat balanced between misleading information and other types of disinformation like fabrication and outright lies. Political parties with higher engagement through disinformation likely enjoy broader influence and reach on social media platforms, influencing public opinion more effectively. PTI's strategy seems more effective in mobilizing social media interactions compared to other parties. PTI and PMLN have seen more organized and active social media teams as they both have shared more than approximately over 10 thousands posts while JI and PPP have lack in this regards with limited posts despite JI has strong engagement. In JI case we have seen the posts that related to protests about common people issues and humanity are more shared and viral.

To explore the next question, the researcher found that misleading information receives the highest number of comments, likes, and shares followed by fabrication with a relatively high comment rate but lower shares, suggesting that fabricated content is discussed more but not shared as widely. As (Recuero & Soares, 2018) study finding revealed that political Conversations on social media are widely shared and received high engagements that included misleading information and fabricated information. Similarly (Allcott & Gentzkow, 2017) study found that fabricated news stories favoring Trump were shared 30 million times in the presidential elections in the United States (2016).

Misleading content's ability to generate viral interactions suggests that it is an especially effective tool for political influence on social media. It creates ambiguity that can persist for a longer time, making it difficult for the public to distinguish fact from fiction. Our finding suggest that disinformation are spread more fast as compare to true news than our these finding are align with (Olan, Jayawickrama, & Suklan, 2022) study that reveled that disinformation and fake news spread more fast and quick with high engagement as compare to true and accurate information. It was determined that disinformation

spreads significantly faster, deeper and more broadly than the truth among all categories of information, and the effects are more pronounced for false political news than for false news about any other area of news beat such as education health, sports, terrorism, natural disasters, science and economy (Vosoughi et al. 2018).

However to explore the next interesting finding that whether prevalence of disinformation increases or not as the elections time approaches, the finding suggests that disinformation spikes during certain periods. We have seen increase in disinformation particularly from late January to February 2024, which was the election time period in Pakistan. Disinformation created some serious concerns for political leaders over security of elections and public trust in the democratic process. This study is align with all the existing literature, as it has been founded by (Recuero & Soares, 2018) that Spread of disinformation increased as the election time come close.

In U.K fake news and disinformation were produce massively on social media platforms that influenced the voting process (Amin & Niaz, 2023). Disinformation is one of the challenging issues and it influence have always been present in politics. (Recuero & Soares, 2018), investigated the Brazilian Presidential Election of 2018 and found that political parties and their followers played an active role in spreading disinformation during election time. Likewise, (Hameleers & Minihold, 2022) argued that disinformation become more noticeable in election days. The spike and increase in disinformation during election time suggest that the prevalence of disinformation increases during sensitive political times and political events, such as election campaigns or social movements. Our finding suggests that the deliberate effort by political leaders of spreading disinformation are increased for political agendas and purposes to build strong narrative in public mind and mobilize them to influence public opinion during a critical political window.

Conclusion

Social media is one of the most powerful soft tool to influence public opinions and people utilize these platforms to engage audience with their align

business, organization and political narrative. Political leaders around the world use social media platforms, like Facebook and twitter to influence public for political agendas and most of the time they were badly exposed to these disinformation techniques. Disinformation is one of the challenging issues and it influence have always been present in politics that created serious concerns for political leaders over security of elections and public trust in the democratic process (Schia & Gjesvik, 2020). And it is one of the challenging issues around the globe as well as in Pakistan. Social media are very useful tool for promotion of democracy, the political parties get very effective platform to communicate with audience. However, alongside its benefits and usefulness, there are negative implications as well. Therefore the researcher aim was to investigate and analyze that to what extent the political parties in Pakistan engage in disinformation while promoting their political agendas and to know various trends and attributes of disinformation develop by political parties in Pakistan.

The researcher also noted that disinformation spikes at key political moments and sensitive political times particularly during election time, it indicating a concentrated and deliberate effort to influence public discourse during significant periods for political gain. Another interesting finding of this study is that we have seen misleading content and fabrication often appears together, creating a blend of truth and falsehood that is harder for public to identify and debunk. In terms of impact, misleading information stands out as the most effective and powerful tool for political manipulation and it has the capability of generating debate, viral engagement and widespread public interaction. The high comment and share rates suggest that misleading information spreads faster and generates more conversations, even if the information is false or deceptive. Fabricated content, while attracting high comment numbers, is shared less. This could suggest that people may recognize some fabrications as false but still engage with them for discussion.

Every study has several limitations, Despite providing important new insights into how political parties in Pakistan practice different attributes of disinformation for political agendas, this study has some limitations, first of all this study has taken only

one Facebook posts of social media platform, the future research may extent the analysis of other social media platforms, secondly this study measured four variables and attributes of disinformation (Outright lie, fabrication, misleading, and potential to harm), the future study may be extended and analyze other variables like sensationalism, parody and satire. The most important recommendation for future researchers to investigate and explored tools that may help to reduce or prevent disinformation on digital platforms. The study offers vital knowledge which is significant in usage of media to prevent disinformation strategies use by political parties and politicians. The findings of the research can be incorporated in the policy making process and future research on disinformation on social media. Thus, a brief policy paper is generated based on the results and findings of the research.

REFERENCES

- Achen, C. H., & Bartels, L. M. (2016). *Democracy for Realists: Why Elections Do Not Produce Responsive Government*. New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
- Ali, Z., & Jan, M. (2013). SOCIAL MEDIA IMPLICATION ON POLITICS OF PAKISTAN; MEASURING THE IMPACT OF FACEBOOK. *The International Asian Research Journal*, 13-21.
- Allcott, H., & Gentzkow, M. (2017). Social Media and Fake News in the 2016 election. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 211-136.
- Amin, N. u., & Niaz, B. (2023). "Media and Hybrid War: Political influence and Disinformation. *Journal of Education & Humanities Research (JEHR)*, 57-64.
- Angus, D., Bruns, A., & Hurcombe, E. (2021). *FAKE NEWS' AND OTHER PROBLEMATIC INFORMATION: STUDYING DISSEMINATION AND DISCOURSE PATTERNS*. Brisbane in Queensland, Australia.: Queensland University of Technology.
- Asubiaro, T. V., & Rubin, V. L. (2017). Comparing features of fabricated and legitimate political news in digital environments (2016-2017). *Proceedings of the Association for Information*, 747-750.
- Bazaco, A. (2019). Clickbait as a strategy of viral journalism: conceptualisation and methods. *RLCS, Revista Latina de Comunicación Social*, 94-115.
- Bennett, W. L., & Livingston, S. (2018). The disinformation order: Disruptive communication and the decline of democratic institutions. *European Journal of Communication*, 122-139.
- Bennett, W. L., & Livingston, S. (2018). The disinformation order: Disruptive communication and the decline of democratic institutions. *European Journal of Communication*, 122-139.
- Bilal, M., & Malik, N. (2019). Profiling Social Media Campaigns and Political Influence: The Case of Pakistani Politics. *13th International Conference on Mathematics, Actuarial Science, Computer Science and Statistics (MACS)*, 1-10.
- Bonow Soares, F., & Recuero, R. (2021). *Hashtag Wars: Political Disinformation and Discursive Struggles on Twitter Conversations During the 2018 Brazilian Presidential Campaign*. Sage, 1-13.
- Brunnmette, J. (2018). The polarization of fake news on twitter. *Sage Journals*, 497-517.
- Caso, L., Cavagnis, L., & Dunbar, N. E. (2023). Cues to deception: can complications, common knowledge details, and self-handicapping strategies discriminate between truths, embedded lies and outright lies in an Italian-speaking sample? *Frontier*, 1-25.
- Cianci, L., & Zecca, D. (2023). *European Journal of Comparative Law and Governance . Polluting the Political Discourse*, 1-46.
- Dehghan, E., & Glazunova, S. (2020). 'Fake news' discourses An exploration of Russian and Persian Tweets. *Journal of Language and Politics*, 741-760.
- Dobber, T. (2020). Do (Microtargeted) Deepfakes Have Real Effects on political attitudes. *The International Journal of Press/Politics*, 69-91.
- E. C. (2018). *Fake News and Online Disinformation*. Belgium: European Union.

- Escolar, M. P., & Lilleker, D. (2023). A Systematic Literature Review of the Phenomenon of Disinformation and misinformation. *Media and Communication*, 76-87.
- Fallis, D. (2015). What Is Disinformation? *Library Trends*, Johns Hopkins University Press, 401-426.
- Farhall, K., & Wright, S. (2019). Political Elites' Use of Fake News Discourse Across Communications Platforms. *International Journal of Communication*, 4353-4375.
- Fathaigh, R. O., & Helberger, N. (2021). THE PERILS OF LEGALLY DEFINING DISINFORMATION. *Internet policy review : Journal of internet regulation*, 1-23.
- Fetzer, J. (2004). Disinformation: The Use of False Information. *mind nad machine*, 231-240.
- Freelon, D., & Wells, C. (2020). Disinformation as Political Communication. *Political Communication*, 145-156.
- Gibbons, A., & Carson, A. (2022). What is misinformation and disinformation? Understanding multi-stakeholders' perspectives in the asia pacific. *Australian Journal of Political Science*, 231-247.
- Green, S. P. (2004). Lying, Misleading, and Falsely Denying: How Moral Concepts Inform the Law of Perjury, Fraud, and False statement. *HASTINGS LAW JOURNAL*, 157-2012.
- GREEN, S. p. (2004). Lying, Misleading, and Falsely Denying: How Moral Concepts Inform the Law of Perjury, Fraud, and False statement. *HASTINGS LAW JOURNAL*, 157-2012.
- Hameleers, M. (2022). Populist Disinformation: Are Citizens With Populist Attitudes Affected Most by Radical Right-Wing Disinformation? *Media and Communication*, 1-12.
- Hameleers, M., & Minihold, S. (2022). *Sage Journals*, 1176-1199.
- Hameleers, M., & Minihold, S. (2022). Constructing Discourses on (Un)truthfulness: Attributions of Reality, Misinformation, and Disinformation by Politicians. *Sage Journals*, 1176-1199.
- Humprech, E., & Esser, F. (2021). The sharing of disinformation in cross-national comparison: analyzing patterns of resilience. *Information, Communication & Society*, 1-15.
- Ida, R., & Saud, M. (2020). An empirical analysis of social media usage, political learning and participation among youth: a comparative study of Indonesia and Pakistan. *Springer Nature*, 1285-1297.
- Igwebuike, E. E., & Chimuanya, L. (2021). Legitimizing falsehood in social media: A discourse analysis of political fake news. *Sage*, 42-58.
- Jerónimo, P., & Sanchez Esparza, M. (2022). Disinformation at a Local Level: An Emerging Discussion. *MDPI*, 1-15.
- Jones, K. (2019). Online disinformation and plottical discourse: Applying human rights framework. *Royal institute of international affairs*, 1-64.
- Kreiss, D., Lawrence, R. G., & McGregor, S. C. (2019). In their own words: Political practitioner Accounts of candidates, audience, affordances, genres and timing in strategic social media use. In *Studying politics across media* (pp. 8-13).
- Krishna, A. (2021). Lacuna publics: advancing a typology of disinformation-susceptible publics using the motivation-attitude-knowledge framework. *Journal of Public Relations Research*, 63-85.
- L. Linvill, D., & L. Warren, P. (2020). Troll Factories: Manufacturing Specialized Disinformation on Twitter. *Political Communication*, 1-21.
- Lanoszka, A. (2019). Disinformation in international politics. *European Journal of International Security*, 1-22.
- M. Hameleers, M. (2020). Populist Disinformation: Exploring Intersections between Online Populism and Disinformation in the US and the Netherlands. *Politics and Governance*, 146-157.
- M. Ortiz, S. (2020). Trolling as a Collective Form of Harassment: An Inductive Study of How Online Users Understand Trolling. *Sage Research Journal*, 1-28.

- Memon, S., & Mahar, S. (2015). Prospects and Challenges for Social Media in Pakistan. *International Conference on Cyber Situation Awareness, Data Analytics and Assessment, London, UK*. (pp. 1- 5). London, UK: IEEE.
- Mir, A., & Mitts, T. (2020). Political Coalitions and Social Media: Evidence from Pakistan. *Perspectives on Politics*, 1-20.
- Muzaffar, M., & Yaseen, Z. (2020). Role of Social Media in Political Campaigns in Pakistan: A Case Study of 2018 Elections. *Journal of Political Studies*, 141-151.
- Olan, F., Jayawickrama, U., & Suklan, J. (2022). Fake news on social media: the impact on society. *Information System Frontier*, 1-16.
- Perez-Curiel, C., & Velasco Molpeceres, A. M. (2020). Impact of political discourse on the dissemination of hoaxes about Covid-19. *Revista Latina de Comunicación Social*, 65-97.
- Piazza, J. A. (2022). Fake news: the effects of social media disinformation on domestic terrorism. *Dynamics of Asymmetric Conflict*, 55-77.
- Recuero, R., & Soares, F. B. (2018). Hyperpartisanship, Disinformation and Political Conversations on Twitter: The Brazilian Presidential Election of 2018. *Association for the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence, AAAI Press* (p. Proceedings of the Fourteenth International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media). Cyprus: AAAI Press.
- Rizi, H. H. (2020). Disinformation Theory in Health Context. *Health Information Management*, 6-43.
- Schaewitz, L., & Flanagin, A. J. (2022). Social Sharing of Political Disinformation: Effects of Tie Strength, Message Valence, and Corrective Information on Evaluations of Political Figures. *Western Journal of Communication*, 1-23.
- Schia, N. N., & Gjesvik, L. (2020). Hacking democracy: managing influence campaigns and disinformation in the digital age. *Journal of Cyber Policy*, 413-428.
- Sharma, K., Ferrara, E., & Liu, Y. (2020). Characterizing Online Engagement With Disinformation and Conspiracies in the 2020 U.S. Presidential Election. *Proceedings of the Sixteenth International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media* (pp. 908-919). Cyprus: AAAI Press, USA.
- Shcherbakova, O., & Nikiforchuk, S. (2023). IDENTIFYING MISLEADING INFORMATION AND TYPES OF FAKES. *scientific journal of polonia university*, 114-118.
- Silverman, C. (2016, 11 17). *BuzzFeed NEWS* . Retrieved from BUZZFEED: <https://www.buzzfeednews.com/article/craigsilverman/viral-fake-election-news-outperformed-real-news-on-facebook>
- Staender, A., & Humprecht, E. (2022). Is Sensationalist Disinformation More Effective? Three Facilitating Factors at the National, Individual, and Situational Level. *Digital Journalism*, 976- 996.
- Tan, C. (2022). Regulating disinformation on Twitter and Facebook. *Griffith Law Review*, 1-23.
- Tomaselli, K. G., & Louw, P. E. (2020). Disinformation and the South African Defence Force's Theory of War. *Social Justice/Global Options*, 124-141.
- Trithara, D. (2020). Securitizing Disinformation: The Case of Westminster's Digital, Culture, Media and Sport Committee. *DEMOCRACY AND SECURITY*, 1-27.
- Varney, S. J. (2018). *House of commons select committee on culture, media and sports 2018, disinformation and fake news interm* . Portsmouth, Ohio, United States: Shawnee State University library guide .
- Wardle, C., & Derakhshan, H. (2018). Thinking About 'Information Disorder': Formats of Misinformation, Disinformation, and mal-Information. *Journalism, 'Fake News' & disinformation*, 43-54.